

Software Requirements Classification: From Bag-of-Words to Transformer

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Abstract. Automated classification of software requirements is valuable for software engineering. Recently, Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques have been utilized as an alternative to manual classification of requirements. In this study, we conduct a thorough empirical evaluation of several NLP methods utilized for efficient classification of software requirements. We focus both on the binary classification between functional and non-functional requirements (NFRs), and on the multi-class classification of the NFRs into specific categories, such as security, performance, usability, etc. For this purpose, we collected and enriched a large dataset of labeled software requirements, paying particular emphasis on security-related requirements. A wide range of NLP-based models were constructed and compared, ranging from simple ML models that utilize the Bag-of-Words (BoW) technique for text representation to the more advanced Large Language Models (LLMs) that emerged recently. The results of our analysis demonstrated the ability of all the examined NLP-based models to provide highly accurate requirements classification both at binary and in multi-class setting, with Transformer-based models demonstrating the best predictive performance, thus revealing the benefits of transfer learning.

Keywords: Requirements Classification · Software Security · Word Embeddings · Transformers · Transfer Learning.

1 Introduction

Software requirements are the foundation of the design of software products. The complete and correct specification of them is crucial in reducing architectural faults, technical debt, bugs, and security issues during the software development life cycle (SDLC) [1]. For instance, incorrect, ambiguous or incomplete specification can lead to the insertion of critical software vulnerabilities in the source code [35]. It is believed that around 50% of the vulnerabilities that a software contains stem from incorrect or vague requirements and design choices, which manifest as security bugs in the source code at later stages of the development [21, 32, 31]. For instance, a misclassified requirement might fail to enforce strong encryption standards, leaving communication channels susceptible to interception. Therefore, a mechanism for automated classification will be crucial for IoT systems

to prevent vulnerabilities from incorrect specifications in the design time of the SDLC, imposing consistent security controls and compliance with regulations. Such a mechanism will mitigate risks and will enhance overall IoT reliability.

A critical aspect of requirements engineering involves accurate requirements classification, as it facilitates a deeper understanding of their purpose, criticality, and the required actions for their implementation. Requirements classification can also find various practical applications, ranging from evaluating the correct definition of Functional Requirements (FRs) and Non-Functional Requirements (NFRs) at the initial stages of software development, to automatic labelling and construction of requirements datasets for future research endeavours. The two main types of software requirements are functional and non-functional [34]. FRs are those which describe the system’s functionalities that are provided to the end-user, while, NFRs are those which report critical quality constraints [12].

Automated requirements classification has attracted researchers’ attention, since manual classification is effort-demanding, error-prone and ambiguous, as texts could be interpreted differently by people [10]. To this end, various text classification techniques have been applied adopting concepts from Natural Language Processing (NLP) [3, 6]. Specifically, Machine Learning (ML) techniques have been used based on simple text representation approaches [26, 33], while recent studies have tried to provide more accurate results by exploiting more advance models such as LLMs [4, 9, 29]. However, as reported by a recent survey [11], existing works focus almost predominantly on a specific dataset, hindering the generalizability of their findings, and on specific LLMs, omitting others that may provide better results.

In this paper, we conduct an empirical evaluation of various NLP techniques, starting with Bag-of-Words (BoW) and working up to the Transformer architecture. Initially, we construct a large software requirements dataset, suitable for binary and multi-class classification, by merging various widely-used requirement datasets and providing proper labeling when necessary. Subsequently, we build various classification models, ranging from ML models that utilize simple NLP techniques to more advanced Transformer-based models that consider deeper contextual information from the requirements text, specifically focusing on the Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT), Bidirectional and Auto-Regressive Transformers (BART), Text-To-Text Transfer Transformer (T5), and Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (GPT). Contrary to the literature that focuses almost predominantly on the encoder-based BERT [11], in the present work, we examine additional Transformer - based models (i.e., GPT, BART), which also utilize the decoder part of the Transformer architecture.

2 Related Work

Many researchers have dealt with the requirements classification task in the software requirements engineering field. Some of them conduct binary classification (functional or non-functional) [2], whereas others are interested in the multi-class classification of NFRs [13] or in both of them [17, 15]. To provide accurate

classifiers, they have utilised various NLP techniques and ML models. Wang et al. [38] utilized logistic regression models to calculate feature values for requirements and then classify security and non-security requirements. Furthermore, Rashwan et al. [27] used the Support Vector Machine (SVM) model to classify NFRs, whereas Rahman et al. [26] used artificial neural networks to accomplish the same task.

Regarding the methods utilized for representing the textual data of requirements, numerous NLP techniques have been examined, as well. Several studies have used a traditional text representation method namely as BoW [6, 20, 34]. Furthermore, Dekhtyar and Fong [3] represented the words of security requirements using word embeddings, and particularly the Word2Vec algorithm, which was originally proposed by Mikolov et al. [22]. These techniques have also been utilized for vulnerability detection with promising results [8].

In order to overcome some drawbacks of the traditional text representation and classification methods, mainly regarding the ability of maintaining the syntactic structure and the semantics of the sentence, researchers have started to adopt Transformer-based approaches [36, 10]. In particular, Khan et al. [13] evaluated multiple Transformer-based models (BERT, DistilBERT, and DistilRoBERTa) to identify and classify NFRs. The evaluation of different Transformer models (BERT, DistilBERT, and RoBERTa) was analysed in the work of Kici et al. [14], as well. Another performance evaluation between traditional classification models and pre-trained models was conducted by Kaur and Kaur [9], who proposed a scheme that performed better than the state-of-the-art models by stacking a Convolutional layer over BERT to enhance its performance.

In a recent systematic mapping study [11], the superiority of Transformer models (in terms of accuracy) is highlighted, suggesting that transfer learning-based approaches outperform the traditional NLP techniques. However, from the aforementioned thorough analysis, two useful insights emerge: (i) the vast majority of studies utilize the PROMISE dataset and (ii) the studies using transfer learning are limited to the use of BERT and its variants. The present study attempts to address these two limitations by (i) proposing an augmented dataset of software requirements labeled with their categories, and (ii) examining also different Transformer-based models, and particularly GPT-2, BART, and T5.

3 Theoretical Background

This section elaborates on the theoretical concepts underlying the technologies used in this study. To begin with, BoW is a foundational text representation method in NLP, consolidating textual data into a "bag" of words irrespective of grammar or order. It constructs a vocabulary from the corpus and represents each document as a vector, with elements corresponding to the actual words and values indicating the frequency of their occurrence in the text. A more complex technique that is widely utilised, is *word embedding*, which represents the meaning of words in a manner where words with similar meanings are positioned closer together in the vector space. In particular, Word2Vec [22] is capable of

learning relationships between words, but at the same time struggles with words out of vocabulary and with learning multiple meanings of the same word.

A more sophisticated technique that could overcome some of the Word2Vec limitations is BERT [4], which is a deep learning technique based on the Transformer architecture. It is considered a deep bidirectional, encoder-only, unsupervised language representation, which generates context-aware embedding vectors, considering the context of a word when learning its vector. Therefore, each word is not represented by a unique vector but the vector can change based on the context. Despite the robust results of BERT, researchers have investigated BERT’s configuration to achieve better results, leading to BERT variants. Through this process, they presented a new model called RoBERTa that consists an improvement to BERT due to the fact that it is trained on an order of magnitude more data from multiple languages than BERT [19]. Another variant of BERT is the DistilBERT model [29], a Transformer that is faster than BERT since it uses knowledge distillation, a technique in which a large model is trained and a smaller model tries to mimic the larger one.

Apart from BERT, other Transformer-based models have emerged recently. GPT is a decoder-only Transformer-based model [24]. In this study, we leveraged the GPT-2, which is the largest open-source GPT variant. Another Transformer model is BART [16], which architecture combines a bidirectional encoder like BERT and a left-to-right decoder similar to GPT. This architecture enables BART to capture bidirectional contextual information during encoding while generating coherent and contextually relevant output sequences during decoding. Similarly, T5 is another encoder-decoder Transformer-based model, introduced by Raffel et al. [25]. T5 was pre-trained on a combination of unsupervised and supervised tasks, where each task was converted to a text-to-text format.

4 Methodology

4.1 Data Collection

For the purpose of this study, we constructed a new dataset¹ by merging data from other software requirement datasets. It consists of five different datasets that contain FRs and NFRs, with additional labels indicating the category in which the NFRs belong (i.e., their Specific Type). This makes the final dataset suitable both for binary and for multi-class requirement classification tasks. In case that labels were missing, manual labeling by the authors was conducted. The overall methodology for constructing the merged dataset is illustrated in Figure 1, along with the following datasets that consist it:

- **PROMISE**: A software engineering repository [18] publicly available for building predictive software models [11].
- **PURE**: A collection of public requirements retrieved from Web [5].

¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/requirementsclassificationwith/>

Fig. 1. Augmented Dataset

- **IoTAC**: A dataset from the work of Riaz et al. [28] that includes well-defined and well-structured security requirements.
- **Kaggle**: A publicly available dataset retrieved from Kaggle [30].
- **SecReq**: An open-source dataset [37] that contains security and non-security requirements from three open-source projects. In this dataset, there was a lack of non-security requirements labels. Therefore, as can be seen in Figure 1, a manual labeling process was performed by the authors identifying whether they are FR or NFR, as well as their specific category in case of NFR (see Table 1).

The final augmented dataset consists of 3471 records and more specifically 2354 NFRs and 1117 FRs. Regarding the NFRs, as already mentioned, they are labelled in specific types such as Security, Usability, Performance, etc. The vast majority of the collected NFRs are security-related, but, for reasons of completeness, we included also other categories in our analysis. In Table 1 the list of the specific types of NFRs that are considered in the dataset is provided.

Table 1. Description of Non-Functional Requirements Specific Type

Acronym	Specific Type	No of records	Percentage(%)
SE	Security	1561	69.59
US	Usability	150	6.68
O	Operability	148	6.59
PE	Performance	139	6.19
LF	Fault Tolerance	84	3.74
MN	Maintainability	46	2.05
SC	Scalability	43	1.91
FT	Fault Tolerance	29	1.29
L	Legal	28	1.24
PO	Portability	15	0.66

4.2 Preprocessing and Model Construction

The overall methodology that was followed is illustrated in Fig. 2. As can be seen by Fig. 2, before proceeding with the construction of the requirement classification models, a careful pre-processing of the data that are included in the

Fig. 2. Methodology

final augmented dataset (see Section 4.1) was necessary. To this end, any requirement records containing null values were initially excluded from the rest of the analysis. Additionally, stop-words and exclamation marks were removed and all the words were transformed to lowercase. Moreover, all the records were processed through lemmatization to reduce a word to its root form (its lemma).

Two classification approaches were considered in this study: (i) a binary, aiming at categorizing requirements in FRs and NFRs, and (ii) a multi-class, with the purpose of identifying and reporting the specific type of NFRs that the text belongs to. Both for the case of binary and multi-class classification, we examine: (i) ML models based on simple text representation techniques (particularly BoW and Word2Vec embeddings), and (ii) advanced pre-trained Transformer models. For the former, we examined various ML algorithms, finding Random Forest as the best performing ML algorithm both for the BoW and for the Word2Vec approaches. For the latter, we examine various Transformer-based models, such as GPT-2, BART, T5, BERT, and BERT’s variants (DistilBERT and RoBERTa).

Regarding the multi-class approach, some of the specific types have very few records, such as fault tolerance (FT) with 29 records and portability (PO) with 15. Therefore, similarly to other relevant research endeavors [10], only the four specific types with the largest number of records were used in order to have a more balanced sample of requirements. In particular, we included in our multi-class analysis the security (SE), usability (US), operability (O) and performance (PE) categories. At this point, we need to clarify that although the majority of the NFRs regard the security category, we perform a multi-class classification in order to examine the ability of our models to discriminate also other categories and not solely to identify which are security requirements.

4.3 Evaluation

For the evaluation of our experiments, the dataset is separated into three parts. Specifically, we kept the 75% of the entire dataset as the training set, and the rest 25% was divided into validation and testing sets. Particularly, we utilize the validation set for tuning our models and selecting the hyperparameters, whereas we use the test set in order to evaluate the produced models in totally unseen

data. We need to mention that during the dataset split we apply a stratified technique to ensure that the three sets retain the original class distribution.

As evaluation measures, we utilize common classification metrics. Specifically, we employ accuracy, recall, precision, and F_1 -score. Since we consider all classes of equal importance, we use the macro-average value of the metrics, which is the most straightforward option of the averaging methods and is equal to the mean of all the per-class scores, without taking the label imbalance into account. We consider F_1 -score as the most critical metric to evaluate and interpret the produced results, as it corresponds to the harmonic mean of precision and recall, and, thus, it considers both false positives and false negatives. Hence, it is the most representative and utilized classification metric for imbalanced datasets [7].

5 Results and Discussion

The results of the model evaluation are presented in Table 2, which reports the performance metrics of the studied models both for binary and multi-class requirements classification. As can be seen by Table 2, although all the examined models manage to predict the category of the analyzed requirements achieving a sufficient F_1 -score, Transformer-based models exhibit better predictive performance (in general) than ML models that are built on simpler NLP techniques.

Particularly, BERT and its variants demonstrate an F_1 -score higher than 90% both in binary and multi-class classification, which is in line with the findings of prior research works [9, 11]. This notice also enhances the generalizability of the findings, since it is validated on a much larger and diverse dataset than those utilized in the literature (i.e., mainly PROMISE). Also, we need to mention that the high accuracy scores in the multi-class scenario demonstrate the capacity of the examined models to recognize efficiently more types of NFRs apart from the security ones, which constitute the majority class.

Table 2. Evaluation Results.

	Binary				multi-class			
Model	F_1	Recall	Precision	Accuracy	F_1	Recall	Precision	Accuracy
BoW	0.90	0.89	0.91	0.92	0.82	0.77	0.89	0.92
Word2Vec	0.84	0.82	0.86	0.87	0.74	0.68	0.91	0.89
BERT	0.90	0.91	0.88	0.91	0.92	0.92	0.93	0.97
DistilBERT	0.90	0.90	0.88	0.90	0.93	0.95	0.91	0.97
RoBERTa	0.91	0.91	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.94	0.90	0.96
BART	0.94	0.94	0.95	0.95	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.96
GPT-2	0.91	0.90	0.92	0.92	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.98
T5	0.92	0.94	0.91	0.93	0.94	0.93	0.95	0.97

Nonetheless, an important observation of the analysis is that GPT-2, T5, and BART present higher accuracy metrics than BERT and its variants. As opposed

to the current trend in the literature, where a strong emphasis is given on BERT [11], other pre-trained models seem to provide similar (or even better) results.

On the contrary, BART is the best performing model in binary classification with F_1 -score of 94%, whereas in multi-class classification GPT-2 demonstrates the best results with an F_1 -score of 95%. This suggests that other Transformer-based models that leverage the decoder part of the Transformer architecture (i.e., GPT-2) or the whole Transformer architecture (i.e., BART), may be more capable in classifying software requirements, and, thus, more elaborate research can be conducted towards this direction.

Furthermore, regarding the comparison between the different utilized methods, we can argue that in both scenarios, Word2Vec proves to be the less accurate method, and BoW is following, whereas Transformer-based models achieve the best results. As described in Section 3, Transformer-based models have context-aware embedding vectors and not global static vectors per word. They can also handle the out-of-vocabulary problem, which stands as a barrier for Word2Vec and BoW, since they use sub-word tokenization [23]. This way, they have a better language understanding than traditional techniques. Moreover, as opposed to the Random Forest classifier that is utilized to classify Word2Vec and BoW representations of requirements, the Transformer model is itself capable of learning long-term dependencies among the words [36, 4, 24].

Interestingly, the ML models that were built based on BoW demonstrate high predictive performance in binary classification that is comparable to the BERT-based models (i.e., 90%). This indicates that FRs and NFRs exhibit highly distinct words that cannot be found in both types of requirements. Finally, we observe that BoW method performs better than Word2Vec, indicating that in these cases the ML classifiers probably focus more on the existence of specific words in the sentences and less on their syntax (i.e., order of the words).

6 Conclusion

In the present paper, an experimental analysis of NLP techniques, ranging from more simplistic methods to the innovative Transformer-based models, in the context of software requirements classification was conducted. Initially, a large dataset of labeled software requirements was constructed by merging information from relevant sources and applying proper labeling, which was then used for building models for requirements classification. The results highlighted the superiority of Transformer-based models, both in binary and in multi-class classification, with previously uninvestigated models (i.e., BART and GPT-2) demonstrating the best predictive performance. Therefore, we recommend further exploration of transfer learning for requirement classification, by evaluating even more Transformer-based architectures. A future challenge would also be leveraging LLMs for categorising security requirements into specific categories.

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